

*Equality Diversity and Inclusion for
Research Enhancement in Bosnia Herzegovina*

EDiRE

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Deliverable abstract

D3.3 contain an analysis of good practices for preparing GEPs in line with EDI principles capitalising on the EDIRE experiences and on the outcomes of the contents of the preliminary guidelines and recommendation on EDI.

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Glossary of abbreviations

BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina

EC - European Commission

ERA - European Research Area

ESR - Early Stage Researcher

EDI - Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion

EU - European Union

GEP - Gender Equality Plan

ORPA - Office for Research and Project Administration

HEI - Higher Education Institution

ICF - International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health

KPIs - Key Performance Indicators

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RFO - Research Financing Organization

RRI - Responsible Research and Innovation

SSST - University Sarajevo School of Science and Technology

TUD - TU Dublin – Technological University Dublin

UCM - Complutense University of Madrid

UniGE - University of Genoa

URCA - University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne

WB - Western Balkans

WP - Work package

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1. Introduction

The significance of aligning the EDIRE project with the gender equality plans of the participants is explicitly emphasised in the HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02 call, highlighting two key requirements:

1. Special attention must be devoted to gender equality objectives, in accordance with the organizations' commitments as outlined in their adopted gender equality plans, and in alignment with ERA objectives as applicable.
2. The comprehensive range of activities to be planned within the project [1] should take into consideration the gender equality plans of the participants, as appropriate.

While developing the EDIRE proposal, the EDIRE partners had already shared information about their GEPs and/or other strategies to promote gender equality and diversity.

The status was as follows:

SSST was in the process of developing its first GEP and expected to have the strategy ready by 2021. The GEP specifically focused on gender diversity in the academic hierarchy and addressed potential issues such as unconscious bias in employment strategies. It took into consideration the specificities of BA, including lower than EU average income and recent history.

UniGE already had a Positive Action Plan, which EIGE recognized as a GEP. The plan covered not only gender mainstreaming and gender equality but also equal opportunities, well-being, and other related topics. UniGE planned to publish a formal GEP by the end of 2021, following the requirements of Horizon Europe.

UCM had a Gender Equality Unit dedicated to cultivating a culture of gender equality within the university community. The unit aimed to ensure the comprehensive application of the principles of equal treatment and equal opportunities. The unit was finalizing a formal GEP, scheduled for online publication by the end of 2021.

TUD already had a GEP as part of the Athena Swan framework.

URCA had a GEP that addressed four priorities: evaluating, preventing, and dealing with the pay gap between women and men; guaranteeing equal access to jobs and different categories; promoting work-life balance; and preventing and addressing sexist and sexual discrimination and violence. As of September 2021, several actions were being implemented, including encouraging women's promotion through mentoring, creating a "good recruitment" guide to combat selection bias, and conducting a survey to measure gender-based and sexual violence.

Therefore, while writing the EDIRE proposal, the expectations were to leverage the partners' extensive experience by conducting a formal analysis and comparison of the collected information. This analysis would serve as the foundation for developing recommendations to

integrate the principles of equality, diversity, and inclusion into the partners' existing GEPs or towards creating new ones.

This deliverable represents an initial step towards meeting these requirements by providing an overview of the progress made in Task 3.4. By facilitating the exchange of knowledge regarding the partners' Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and fostering a dialogue on the inclusion of best practices, it will be possible, in future EDIRE activities, to establish connections between various initiatives and those implemented at the local level through the GEPs. These results will inform the planning of new initiatives within EDIRE and future updates of each GEP.

[1] Activities should include, at least, the following: a) short-term staff exchanges; b) expert visits and short-term on-site or virtual training; c) workshops; d) conference attendance; e) organisation of joint summer school-type activities; f) dissemination and outreach activities.

1.1 The creation of D 3.3: GEP Committee

The activities for Task 3.4, which commenced in December 2022, were led by UniGE. The initial step involved establishing a GEP Committee comprising individuals from various partner universities who possessed expertise and knowledge of GEPs. This committee would oversee the task throughout its duration. The designated committee member from each university was also responsible for organising local networking activities and gathering/uploading data.

By December 9th, 2022, each university had appointed a representative for the GEP Committee. UniGE was represented by Rita Bencivenga and Carla Maria Reale (who were also responsible for task implementation and coordination), Sara Clavero represented TUD, Jasminka Hasic Telalović represented SSST, Zahia Guessoum represented URCA, and Clara Sanchez-Rebato Valiente represented UCM.

The first meeting of the GEP Committee took place on December 19th, 2022. During this meeting, the partners discussed the overall framework of the activities outlined in Task 3.4 and organized further work. The committee decided to convene monthly to exchange information on the partners' GEPs, compare them, and agreed to collect and map data using overview tables.

2. Compare and study partners GEP

During the second and third meetings, partner universities presented and discussed the GEPs implemented in their respective institutions. On January 27th, 2023, UniGE, UCM, and SSST presented their GEPs, followed by TUD and URCA presenting theirs on February 3rd, 2023. These meetings offered valuable opportunities for the partners to compare their GEPs and explore the various national systems addressing EDI (Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion) issues within their research institutions. Moreover, these meetings served as the initial step towards sharing knowledge and exchanging good practices among the partners.

In between meetings, and after the last online meeting, through direct contacts among partners upon request, intense work at partner levels allowed for debate regarding task contents, activities, results and future impacts.

Moreover, to facilitate the collection of data and their comparison, UniGE created an overview table to be filled in by partner universities.

Table 1 summarises the target grounds for discrimination and macro areas in which each partner will monitor EDI.

Each partner institution already works on gender, as this is the core of the task. However, partners could decide to map initiatives intersecting gender with other grounds of potential discrimination. This table shows how most of the involved universities are working on expanding their EDI grounds. Most of them already cover disability (UniGE, UCM, URCA, TUD) and sexual orientation (UniGE, URCA, TUD), while only UniGE and TUD are working on gender identity/expression and race and ethnicity. None of the partner institutions currently address age and religion/belief as target areas in their EDI strategies.

	SSST	UniGE	UCM	URCA	TUD
Gender	X	X	X	X	X
Gender identity/expression		X			X
Ethnic and racial origin		X			X
Age					
Disability		X	X	X	X
Sexual orientation		X		X	X
Religion or belief					

Table 1: Overview of target grounds for discrimination and macro areas in which each partner will monitor EDI

3. Collecting best practices on EDI: exchange of knowledge amongst partner universities

EDIRE Partners analysed and assessed the state-of-play within each partner institution (see Annex A for details). At the beginning of the project, partners collected information about the situation in their organisation. By the end of the task/project, each partner will have progressed in gender equality and EDI practices and this initial collection will help in planning future gender equality and EDI related initiatives.

Following the work done to identify the current EDI related practices and actions in each University, the partners chose which topics, addressed by others, they wanted to know more about (see Annex B).

In other words, SSST and the other partners are interested in further exploring specific initiatives within the GEPs and, more broadly, in the partner universities. These initiatives have been described in the following pages as best practices.

Where further exploration or practical guidance will be needed to implement some of these best practices, the EDIRE project will include such activities and make them as public and accessible as possible for anyone interested. The upcoming GEPs of the partners will bear the traces of this activity through the inclusion of new actions or the reformulation of existing ones.

4. Best practices from TUD

4.1 Race equity

Race Equity in the Irish HEA sector

The Irish universities Association (IUA) has worked with the Higher Education Authority (HEA) on the development of a race equality implementation plan, published in September 2022. The plan aims to advance race equality work across the sector, and one of the key actions included in the implementation plan is the development of a national statement of Anti Racism Principles higher education institutions.

Race Equity in TU Dublin

Equality Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) works across TU Dublin to advance EDI and to build an inclusive culture, promote equality, prevent discrimination and protect the human rights of staff, students, and everyone affected by EDI policies and plans. TU Dublin is committed to actively fostering an inclusive, diverse, safe, and respectful institutional culture. This commitment, embedded in the TU Dublin Strategic Intent 2030, is informed by Sustainable Development Goal 4 to ‘ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.’

TU Dublin’s vision and commitment to Race Equity is stated as follows:

“We will build an intercultural university that is anti-racist and facilitates a true sense of belonging and empowerment for all members of the university community. We will do this through researched evidence, education, awareness-raising, understanding, and active engagement with one another, with the historical, structural, institutional, and individual dimensions of racism, and with the needs of our local and global communities.”

TU Dublin’s Plan for Race Equity identifies institutional priorities to deliver foundational progress as listed below:

1) Research and innovation:

- Research best practice approaches to report and support (including transformative justice resolution mechanisms)

2) Education and awareness-raising:

- Existing equality modules for staff will be reviewed, updated, and integrated so that they take account of the four dimensions of racism/discrimination as relevant;
- TU Dublin will achieve University of Sanctuary status by January 2023.

3) Embedding a race equity mindset:

- All Schools will have adopted an agreed Framework for Diversifying the Curriculum by September 2023.
- Adopt best practice approaches that do not only rely on natural justice i.e., also take a transformative justice approach

Race Equity Community of Practice

An example of a Race Equity good practice is the Race Equity Community of Practice (CoP) in TU Dublin. This CoP enables:

1. Deepening knowledge of the dimensions of racism and taking an intersectional approach to address inequalities and implement structural change.
2. Robust understanding of the intersectional dimensions of discrimination and harm.
3. Acknowledging harm and what healing from harm involves.
4. Transferring knowledge to practice, with the goal of continually working to become anti-racist educators and practitioners.
5. TU Dublin educators, practitioners, and students to be leaders in this field, contributing to the sectoral and national move away from primarily individualized understandings of racism (related to 'good' or 'bad' people) and toward understandings of racism, and other forms of harm and discrimination, as structural and requiring personal and societal transformation.

TU Dublin supports members of the Race Equity CoP to develop their expertise in identifying and addressing all four dimensions of harm and discrimination (historical, structural, institutional, and individual); incorporate learnings into their own work; and share it with students, TU Dublin colleagues and colleagues across the Irish HEI sector. This CoP is underpinned by learning, embedding, and sharing EDI principles in TU Dublin and beyond. Regarding learning, seminars, and workshops are hosted where participants learn from subject matter experts; affected communities; and academics. To embed race equity CoP members, bring their skills and understanding back to their work at TU Dublin. Regarding sharing knowledge and best practices, findings and tools are disseminated to wider networks through conference papers, practitioners' networks and community groups. The Race Equity CoP contributes to building an accessible university; building connected communities; and engaging staff, students, and practitioners in becoming anti-racist educators (People Objectives). This CoP contributes to addressing racism across the university thus enabling constructive and egalitarian international partnerships in the future, and the enrolment and retention of international students (Partnership Objective).

Key activities proposed for the Race Equity CoP 2023/24 include: mapping all anti-racism initiatives and activities that Race Equity CoP members are engaged with; issuing a call for additional members via the EDI Update and targeting areas in the university where there are few to no members; run campus workshops in line with Race Equity objectives; engage with disseminating good practice responses to far-right disinformation. The plans include collecting data on the experiences of students from Roma, Traveller, Black and Minority Ethnic Communities in Ireland to better understand their experiences and further develop effective initiatives that enhance the student learning experience and build inclusive and anti-racist learning environments (2024).

Another example of a Race Equity good practice is how the Community Development and Youth Work (CDYW) program team in TU Dublin has embedded anti-racism across the programme since September 2020, equipping students with the skills to identify and address racism at multiple levels - individual, cultural and structural. Furthermore, the good practices implemented at TU Dublin at the institutional level aim at ensuring Race Equity at TU Dublin including restorative justice practices and conflict resolution mechanisms.

References/Further reading

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<https://www.restorativepracticesireland.ie/>

<https://www.southampton.ac.uk/~assets/doc/hr/Five%20methods%20for%20managing%20conflict.pdf>

4.2 Universal Design for transformative learning

Universal Design (UD) can be traced back to American architect, product designer and educator Ron Mace, and defined as “the design and composition of an environment so that it can be accessed, understood and used to the greatest extent possible by all people regardless of their age, size, ability or disability” (McNutt & Craddock, 2021 p. 177). UD is underpinned by seven principles: equitable use; flexibility in use; simple and intuitive; perceptible information; tolerance for error; low physical effort; size and space for approach and use (McNutt & Craddock, 2021 p. 177-178). A UD approach aids independence and social participation for all via “continual improvement in all contexts” (McNutt & Craddock, 2021 p. 176).

UD systems recognise that there are “multiple layers within the ecological framework that affect human development” particularly in the educational ecosystem (McNutt & Craddock, 2021 p. 178). Firstly, at the micro level individual needs and abilities are provided for via “teaching practices, classroom design and layout, technologies including assistive technologies, [l]earning resources and spaces” (Ibid, 2021 p. 178). Thus, the focus of

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education is re-orientated to being student focused and towards student involvement in co-designing their own education. Secondly, the institutional (meso) level covers “governance, policies and procedures” and links with both community-based initiatives and families as they are both recognised as important in developing and sustaining innovative learning (McNutt & Craddock, 2021 p. 179). Thirdly, the macro level is concerned with “establishing directives, legislative acts, developing standards, promoting awareness and ensuring the diffusion of universal design and its adoption at national and local educational system levels” (McNutt & Craddock, 2021 p. 179). UD in education is discussed further below.

Universal Design in Education

In education, UD is understood as “the creation of an environment which can be accessed by all and enables full engagement, progression and success for all students” (PATH report). It was initially a design approach predominately focused on accommodating people with disabilities. However, since its inception, UD has been significantly developed and transformed, and now offers a framework for the inclusion of all students in education.

Implementing UD in the education sphere removes the need to label students as requiring special support to include them in education by proactively adopting approaches to inclusion as opposed to relying on “reactive approach[es]” that provide “bespoke solutions or temporary fixes” (PATH Report). A UD framework “embeds flexibility and choice for students turning the deficit model on its head” by weaving “inclusion into the fabric of the student experience” and by encouraging “a reflective, inclusive approach” that, identifies and removes the barriers/potential barriers to engaging diverse student cohorts (PATH Report). Universal Design for Learning (UDL) provides “multiple means of representation; multiple means of action and expression; and multiple means of engagements to help create expert learners” (Kinsella, 2018 p. 107). A UDL approach can enable transforming the education sphere “from an inequitable learning environment [...] to a more holistic student-centric experience” (McNutt & Craddock, 2021 p. 176).

Universal Design for Transformative Learning (UDL) in TU Dublin

A key strategic objective of TU Dublin is to become “the most ‘accessible’ university in Ireland, with the largest number of diverse learners” (TU Dublin Strategic Intent-2030).

The Programme for Access to Higher Education (PATH) program was established in 2016 in Ireland to deliver the equity of access objectives. The PATH program supports implementing the National Access Plan (NAP) objectives by providing funding to higher education institutions (HEIs) to deliver innovative measures to improve participation and retention of specific target groups in higher education. Currently, PATH is in its fourth phase – PATH4 and there are two strands in this phase. The first strand is concerned with supporting inclusive universally designed higher education environments for all students, while the second strand concentrates on course provision for students with Intellectual Disabilities.

For many years, TU Dublin (and before DIT) has been actively working towards embedding the UDL framework for HEIs to develop expert learners in their institution. One example of this are capstone projects to embed UDL including the ‘Connected Voices in Learning Exhibition’

to celebrate the diversity of people in HEIs via the UDL lens (<https://www.ahead.ie/journal/Connected-Voices-in-Learning-Exhibition>).

Within TU Dublin, the Universal Design for Education (UDE) and the UDL spaces are dynamic and open to change and adaptation. Teaching UD modules, particularly to first year undergraduates, is a way of embracing and embedding UDL in TU Dublin. Indeed, the integration of UDL principles may lead to transformation institutionally as well as on an individual micro level for students.

On 1st March 2023, a staff development course on UDL was launched as part of the EU+ alliance, of which TU Dublin is a member. The course provides educators with a strong introduction to the universal design for learning framework and gives them the opportunity to implement UDL approaches within their teaching and learning activities.

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TU Dublin Strategic Intent Strategic Intent 2030 | TU Dublin

4.3 Gender identity and gender expression policy

TU Dublin aims to create a supportive and inclusive environment in which all gender identities are welcome and transphobic behaviour and bullying is never tolerated. TU Dublin recognizes that gender identity, gender expression, and any transition journeys, are unique to individuals. Furthermore, TU Dublin is committed to supporting students and staff at all stages of their transition journey. This policy lays out how we give effect to that commitment. It is part of the larger suite of equality, equal opportunities, diversity, and inclusion policies at the University.

This policy applies to:

- All applicants for employment, employees, and former employees.
- All student applicants, students, alumni, and student union officers

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- All service users, third party contractors, visitors, customers and clients of the University

The primary objective of the policy is to recognise gender identity and expression as a positive core part of being human. The policy sets out an overarching framework in which equal rights and opportunities are accorded to diverse gender identities and expressions, facilitating a work and study environment free from discrimination and harassment.

This policy:

- provides guidelines for availing of supports in a gender transition process;
- provides guidelines for supporting persons in our community who wish to embark on, or are already undertaking, a gender transition process;
- outlines organisational structural supports to promote awareness, understanding and learning around gender identity and gender expression within the TU Dublin community.

Rights and responsibilities

All members of the TU Dublin community have the right to:

- Be treated with fairness, dignity and respect, express one's gender identity freely, and not be disadvantaged due to gender identity or expression.
- Privacy and confidentiality with disclosure of information only with consent.
- Raise concerns with the expectation that they will be reasonably addressed in accordance with the spirit of this policy.
- Equal access to employment, education, services, training, and promotional opportunities.
- Access to activities and facilities appropriate to their gender identity.
- Reasonable and appropriate arrangement and accommodations.
- Access to the appropriate knowledge, skills and expertise to enable both students and staff to be supported at all stages of their transition journey.

All managers (including lecturers) have a primary responsibility to:

- Understand, support, and champion the Gender Identity & Gender Expression policy. Managers are accountable for implementing this policy in a manner that fully complies with all its requirements.
- Take all reasonable steps (e.g., undertake training) to create an inclusive team environment free from discrimination, to provide appropriate and reasonable support to team members, and to ensure that gender identity and gender expression are respected.
- Ensure training in relation to gender identity and expression is prioritised and provided on team- based approach as appropriate.

- Seek appropriate advice and guidance from the Directorate of Equality Diversity & Inclusion to assist in supporting a person who is exploring or questioning their gender identity.
- Comply with relevant legislation.

Guidelines for supporting persons in a gender transition process

TU Dublin recognises that:

- All staff and students should be fully supported to participate in TU Dublin activities, clubs and societies in accordance with their gender identity.
- A person should have access to their preferred choice of toilet and changing facilities at the point when they start to live in their preferred gender. The university will strive to ensure that gender neutral bathrooms and changing rooms are provided throughout each campus. Plans for all new buildings should provide for gender neutral bathrooms and changing rooms.
- Transition including medical transition, may not be applicable, necessary or desirable for all transgender individuals for a variety of reasons.
- Medical interventions related to transition are not elective.
- People who transition at work or who identify as transgender or non-binary in a professional environment may face unique challenges (e.g., unnecessary or invasive questions when accessing services).
- Although the university is obliged to maintain records that include an individual's legal name and legal gender, the university will use the name and gender preferred by the individual to such an extent as is possible under the current legal framework.
- One of the most significant moments will be when the individual wishes to start presenting in their chosen gender publicly. It is crucial that this is managed and communicated well to those who have a working relationship with the individual. Different individuals will have different needs, and there is no set, standard model of transition. The key person or other relevant person, working with the individual and their colleagues and peers, will facilitate this in line with the Confidential Implementation Plan.
- Staff who work in a supporting role to persons who are transitioning will require adequate training and ongoing supervision.
- Members of the TU Dublin community who are in a supporting role of someone who is transitioning (e.g., a family member) will require reasonable accommodations and support.

Availing of support in a gender transition process

TU Dublin provides support via a 'key persons' system. For further information see Gender Identity and Gender Expression document or contact equality@tudublin.ie to view their contact details.

A 'key person' will meet the person needing support and outline the full range of supports available in TU Dublin; and assist in drawing up a 'Confidential Implementation Plan' (CIP) for the period of transition or thereafter. The implementation plan will be reviewed and reassessed regularly. The plan will include the following items, where applicable:

- The expected point or phase of change of name, personal details or gender marker.
- Who will need to be informed initially, and the level of information to be provided, in order to offer support and arrangements during the transition process.
- Whether you wish to inform your relevant contacts yourself (e.g., line managers, clients, tutors, peers), or if you would prefer this to be done for you.
- What amendments will be required to records and systems.
- Whether training or briefing for your peers and line managers/tutors will be necessary, at what point and by whom this will be carried out.
- If applicable, the expected timing of any medical and surgical procedures (if any) whilst recognising that timeframes can change.
- If applicable, what time off will be required for treatment and/or how possible side effects from any medication may affect your job/studies and any arrangements needed.
- If applicable, information on supports you can access (e.g., peer support group).

Gender identity and gender expression support for students

1) Student Records

- Initially, students can only be added to TU Dublin records using their legally recorded name.
- Under the Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy students are able to change their recorded name and/or gender on most university systems - with or without legal documentation - if they apply to do so by filling out a Change of Student Records Request Form 2022/23 or contacting a Key Person whose details are at the end of this document.
- No records will be changed without the written permission of the individual as part of a Confidential Implementation Plan (CIP). All records will be changed in a coordinated way across multiple services, it may take time to prepare for a coordinated change in front-facing records.
- Some records cannot be changed without the provision of legal documentation and these will be noted to you.
- If you wish to change your recorded name outside of the Gender Identity and Gender Expression policy process you need to provide legal evidence of a change of name.

- Students are advised to refer to the Data Protection Notice for Students which explains how TU Dublin collects, stores, uses and shares your personal data, and your rights in relation to the data held.

2) Outcomes

A change to front-facing records will result in:

- Updated ID cards (these are not legal documents and TU Dublin has no control over whether they are accepted as a form of valid identification outside the university).
- Updated student profile.
- The new name associated with an individual's addresses (email/permanent/study addresses) and letters will be sent using the newly recorded name.
- Changes to relevant local records e.g., class lists

3) Activities, Clubs and Societies

All students are fully supported to participate in TU Dublin activities, clubs and societies in accordance with their gender identity. This applies to sports and/or teams in particular. The university will strive to ensure that gender-neutral bathrooms and changing rooms are provided across the university. From 2021 all new buildings will have gender-neutral bathrooms and changing rooms installed. Existing buildings and those under construction will be retrofitted insofar as possible.

4) Facilities (changing rooms, toilets, etc)

All individuals are supported to use changing facilities and toilets in accordance with their gender identity. A person should have access to their choice of toilet and changing facilities at the point when they start to live in their gender. It is not acceptable to restrict a trans person from using disabled toilets or other gender-neutral facilities. That said providing the option can be helpful for trans, non-binary, and intersex people, and some prefer to use gender-neutral facilities.

5) Dress Codes

Dress codes impact all trans, non-binary, intersex, and gender non-conforming people. Any official dress codes, where relevant, should use gender-neutral language. If a person is transitioning, then the University will engage with the individual on the issue (if applicable in the circumstances) and relevant agreements will be included in the CIP.

6) Accommodation

Any accommodation arrangements related to field trips or placements should be in line with an individual's gender identity if relevant. Where possible single occupancy accommodation should be available if needed. The University will engage with the individual on the issue (if applicable in the circumstances) and relevant agreements will be included in the CIP.

4.4 Reporting harm or discrimination

All members of the University Community have the right to study and work in an environment free from all forms of bullying and harassment including racism, sexual misconduct, homophobia, and transphobia. Students, employees, and visitors to TU Dublin can report harm or discrimination via the **Speak Out reporting tool**.

This is an online anonymous reporting tool available for students and staff, to disclose incidents of bullying, cyberbullying, harassment, discrimination, hate crime, coercive behaviour/control, stalking, assault, sexual harassment, sexual assault, and rape. The aim of this tool is to collect data to assist the university in the implementation of educational and policy initiatives and to signpost the victim/survivor to the support services that can help them should they wish to seek help. **The Speak Out reporting tool is completely anonymous.** TU Dublin has no way to identify or contact any member of the university community who uses the tool. The tool will help to find information and contact details on relevant supports and specialist external supports.

5. Best practices from UniGE

5.1 Gender balance report

Gender balance report in Italy

In Italy, in 2007, the Directive of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers of 23 May 2007 “Measures to implement equality and equal opportunities between men and women in public administrations” was enacted. The Directive recommended the use of Gender Balance reports in all public administrations, while the Legislative Decree 27 October 2009, n. 150, mentioned this document as an essential part of the performance plan. Art. 10 of this Legislative Decree requires each Italian Public organisation to indicate, in their annual performance report, the organisational and individual results achieved for the programmed objectives and resources as well as the gender balance achieved.

The National Conference of Equality Bodies of Italian Universities and the Working Group for Gender Budgeting (born within the Conference of Italian University Rectors - CRUI) drafted the Guidelines for Gender Balance Reports in Universities [[https://www2.cruil.it/cruil/Linee Guida Bilancio di Genere negli Atenei italiani.pdf](https://www2.cruil.it/cruil/Linee_Guida_Bilancio_di_Genere_negli_Atenei_italiani.pdf)] in 2019. The Gender Balance Report is a document that, on one hand, captures the gender distribution of various components within the University, as well as the participation of women and men in the University's governing bodies. On the other hand, it monitors the University's actions towards gender equality and assesses the impact of these actions and the University's policies, including financial commitments, on women and men. The working group of experts developed the guidelines and methodology for creating the Gender Report of Universities, thus facilitating its widespread dissemination among Italian universities and the comparability of the documents produced.

Gender Balance Report in UniGE

The objective of preparing the first Gender Balance Report of the University of Genoa as envisaged in the 2017-2020 Positive Action Plan, was to provide the University with a tool for detecting and analysing data collected at local and national levels, to evaluate the impact on women and men of the policies implemented by the University and to allow for the planning of actions aimed at remedying situations of inequality.

The UniGE Gender Balance Report follows the structure recommended by the CRUI document and adopted by other Italian Universities. It contains:

- context analysis, through identifying a set of data, indicators, indices, and their representations that allow historical, national, and international comparability.
- the University's actions to pursue various objectives related to gender equality and protecting potentially discriminated subjects.
- how the Gender Balance Report fits into the budget cycle and the University planning documents.

The UniGE Gender Balance Report made use of the indicators, the tables of correspondences, the examples of gender indices proposed by Italian Universities and the various acronyms and abbreviations which are appendices of the CRUI guidelines, helpful in drafting the Gender Balance report and, above all, for standardising the data collected from multiple Italian universities.

Examples of recommendations emerging from the data collection and analysis:

Students:

- Actions to encourage high school female students to enrol in STEM degree courses, above all in engineering and computer science.
- Strengthen guidance, counselling and tutoring services aimed at students to intercept any discomfort and problems regarding their studies, which affect the male percentage of students more.

Teaching and research staff:

- The data on research funding show a situation that varies from year to year for UniGE teachers: the constant monitoring envisaged by the Gender Balance Report is therefore necessary.
- Need for an in-depth review of the research projects presented and selected for funding, extending the field to university spin-off projects.
- Expand the field of investigation to include family leave to evaluate the impact of care work on women's careers, especially concerning age and role.

- Correlate the data referred to in the previous point with national and international publications. The number of publications is, in fact, one of the most used metrics to evaluate a teacher's productivity.
- Initiate further surveys to explore teachers' relationship with their work through questionnaires that examine awareness of gender issues, the reconciliation of private life and work and the presence or absence of these issues in the teachings.

Administrative staff:

- It is necessary to start a reflection on spaces, times, and methods of the work of TABS staff to reduce the remaining disparities in gender equality. Collecting further, more detailed data on family leave, and teleworking is necessary.

The UniGE Gender Balance Report for 2020 is available (in Italian) at: <https://cpo.UniGE.it/node/177>.

A methodological note: all the data refer to the 2020 calendar year (with reference, where possible, to 12.31.2020) or to the 2019/2020 academic year unless otherwise indicated.

5.2 Policy on Harassment and Discrimination

The University of Genoa (UniGE) has several structures and strategies to prevent and combat gender-based violence. The Confidential Counsellor (Consigliera di Fiducia) and Garante di Ateneo (Ombudsman (point 1) and the Code of Conduct for the prevention of all forms of discrimination, harassment, and mobbing in the workplace and study (point 2) are directly linked to these activities. The Code of Ethics (point 3) partly reinforces the planned measures. Agreements and Protocols are also implemented with other bodies and institutions in the Region (point 4), and conferences and seminars discuss the topic, as shown by the example further provided (point 5).

1. The Confidential Counsellor and the Ombudsman

The counsellor is an impartial figure aimed at preventing, managing and helping resolve cases of bullying and harassment in the university, brought to their attention by any university community member. (<https://unige.it/commissioni/consulente-di-fiducia>)

The Confidential Counsellor:

- Carries out listening and assistance activities for the protection of anyone belonging to the UniGE community who considers themselves a victim of mobbing and/or harassment by another member of UniGE community, that occurred in a place of study or work of UniGE.
- Proposes to the administration any actions aimed at preventing situations of discomfort in the working environment and/or at overcoming such situations.
- Interacts with the bodies responsible for supporting the Administration in defining suitable strategies to promote the improvement of the quality of organisational coexistence.

- Monitors any risk situations, carrying out activities to detect discomforts also through the organisation of special meetings with the various components operating within UniGE.
- Proposes appropriate actions and training and information initiatives aimed at promoting an organisational climate that ensures the equal dignity and freedom of the people working in the University.
- Participates, upon request, in meetings of the CUG (Comitato Unico di Garanzia) and CPO (Comitato per le Pari Opportunità)
- Reports annually on the activities carried out within UniGE.

The University Ombudsman

The University Ombudsman is appointed by the Academic Senate, with a majority of eligible voters, upon the proposal of the Rector. The term of office is four academic years and is not renewable. The Ombudsman is chosen from individuals with particular qualifications external to the University, who have never held an indefinite-term position or have an employment relationship with the University. If such a relationship is established, the Ombudsman is removed from office.

The Ombudsman examines individual complaints concerning acts and behaviours, including omissions, of bodies, structures, offices, or individuals belonging to the University.

The Ombudsman communicates their observations to the complainant and the Rector, and if deemed appropriate, to other parties involved and the University's bodies or structures.

Presents an annual report to the governing bodies of the University.

2.The Code of Conduct for the prevention of all forms of discrimination, harassment, and bullying in the workplace and workplace

The Confidential Counsellor ensures the application of the code of conduct, a document that defines the concepts of discrimination, harassment, and bullying, describes informal and formal procedures and details the principle of confidentiality.

3.UniGE's code of ethics

On 16 December 2011, UniGE issued the code of ethics, as prescribed by Law no. 240/2010. The code formalises many principles discussed in the previous years, both in the political and cultural debate on the reorganisation of the university system.

Adopting this code is not just a formal obligation or a charter of values with no actual application but a reorganisation tool for the academic community, shared by all its components and aimed at standardising its actions. This code of ethics sets out rules of conduct, creating a behavioural model to be adopted and inspired by. The University's code of ethics also contains sanctions and procedures for ascertaining violations. In particular, Article 3 - Rejection of all forms of discrimination and harassment, also explicitly refers to sexual harassment. The existence of an asymmetrical position between the perpetrator and

the victim of harassment or discrimination, including harassment and sexual harassment, constitutes an aggravating circumstance in violating the ethical rule. The University ensures that victims of discrimination, and in particular victims of harassment, whether sexual or otherwise, receive prompt and appropriate protection, free from any prejudice and respectful of the confidentiality of the persons involved.

https://UniGE.it/sites/contenuti.UniGE.it/files/imported/regolamenti/org/documents/decreto497_codice_etico.pdf (In Italian)

4. Protocols and agreements

In 2022, UniGE signed an agreement to prevent and combat violence against women, minors and vulnerable persons in the Liguria Region, 'Inrete contro la violenza', which commits, in addition to the University of Genoa, several other bodies in the Ligurian territory.

The protocol is based on the idea that, to combat the phenomenon of violence against women, minors and vulnerable persons in the family, there is a need both for organic intervention by the institutions to support the victims and for action that can bring to light potential cases of repeated and habitual violence that would otherwise remain concealed.

Among the new features, the protocol is extended to Anti-violence Centres, shelters and rehabilitation centres for abusive men. The protocol allows the judicial authority to consult the A.Li.Sa database, which keeps track of access at regional hospitals or emergency rooms.

Each party is bound to specific commitments and might sign a separate implementation agreement with the facilities concerned. These will provide for organisational and management aspects, security, and insurance coverage. The protocol will last four years, renewable for four years by written agreement.

5. Organisation of seminars or initiatives to combat gender-based violence

The Inter-University Research Group 'Political Subjectivity of Women' organised the seminar 'INTERVENTION STRATEGIES AGAINST VIOLENCE ON WOMEN.

THE E.V.A. (acted violence examination) PROTOCOL for the detection of cases of domestic violence'. (The E.V.A. protocol is a State Police protocol guidelines in case of intervention for domestic violence. The seminar was part of the national initiative 'CONTRASTING VIOLENCE ON WOMEN. A COMMITMENT INSIDE THE UNIVERSITY.)

6. Best practices from UCM

6.1 Build gender awareness into Research Design & Practice

The II Gender Equality Plan encourages the inclusion of gender equality awareness in the research design and practice. The document promotes the inclusion of a minimum of 40% of women researchers in national or international research projects. If this aspect is not included, the researcher in charge of the project is asked why a gender perspective is not included and

they will have to justify their decision to omit a gender perspective. In addition, UCM research groups must also promote the inclusion of a minimum of 40% of women. If this percentage is not reached, this decision needs to be explained, and submitted when the group's accreditation is requested. This form will also have to be filled in subsequent hiring.

6.2 DOCENTIA-UCM and gender perspective

The DOCENTIA program¹ establishes a comprehensive framework where Spanish universities can elaborate their own teaching evaluation models in order to follow the current legislation as well as the rules related to the quality of higher education institutions set by The European Higher Education Area.

The program DOCENTIA-UCM is the quality evaluation system specifically applied to Universidad Complutense de Madrid and its contexts. The inclusion of a gender perspective in this evaluation program means that the students can evaluate if their professors, while preparing and imparting their lectures, do so through a gender perspective or if the professor is aware of the importance of a gender perspective as well as the use of inclusive language among other gender perspective related topics. The idea is to allow students to evaluate their professors, male and female, in how they adopt a gender perspective.

This program also has a self-assessment function for professors. The system allows professors to justify and evaluate themselves and how they include a gender perspective in their courses, how they have added it to their classes and/or what aspects they need to improve in order to establish a gender perspective in their courses.

6.3 GE in language/cultural courses

Language and cultural courses also include Gender Equality². The Spanish Language Unit works towards including GE through language in the courses they teach. Some Professors in this unit test students to see if they know the possibilities of language to allow women visibility and to see if the students use these new language options.

6.4 Gender pay audit

According to its Unidad de Igualdad (Gender Equality Unit)³, the UCM is the Spanish public university with the least wage gap in Spain. While the Ministry of University conducted a gender pay audit two years ago, in order to create the current GEP, the UCM did a second

¹ This information was provided by Ángel L. Rubio, responsible of the DOCENTIA-UCM program of the *Facultad Ciencias de la Información* (Information Science School).

² Covered this topic Teresa Maria Ramallle, professor and *Vicedecana de Estudios y Planificación Docente de la Facultad de Ciencias de la Información* (Vice-Dean of Studies and Teaching Planning of the Information Science School). Ramalle is also part of the Spanish Language Unit of the School.

³ The information shown in this section was delivered by Isabel Tajahuerce, who is the *Delegada del Rector para la Igualdad* (Rector's delegate for Gender Equality) and also the head of the Unidad de Igualdad (Gender Unit).

gender pay audit as a preliminary study of the institution. It is recommended to do this type of auditory every two years.

6.5 Policy against gender-based and sexual violence

The UCM is a member of the National Treaty of Estate Against Gender-Based Violence. According to the UCM II GEP, following this treaty the university agreed to prevent, detect and act when gender-based violence situations occur in its institution.

UCM has detected that the most common types of gender-based violence that occurs in the academic field are sexism and sexual harassment. The UCM II GEP has a chapter completely dedicated to this type of violence.

To make victims feel supported, the II GEP formally established the Dispositivo de Atención Psicológica (Psychological Attention Device) inside the Unidad de Igualdad (Gender Equality Unit). This section was created to accompany, orientate, advise and assist the victims from the moment the case is notified to the Unidad de Igualdad (Gender Equality Unit), independently of the existence of a police report or not.

In addition, to this device, the Dispositivo para de Atención Social (Social Attention Device) of the Gender Equality Unit is also added as a protocol tool to evaluate each situation individually and to detect if the people involved have specific needs to be covered during the process, as a way to prevent risks.

These two tools of the Unidad de Igualdad (Gender Equality Unit) are also activated during cases of physical or physiological aggression, in or outside of a romantic relationship, supporting women of the university community independently of whether they have submitted a police report in relation to the aggression they have experienced.

At the same time, training courses will be offered to teach the victims and their inner circle on how to detect dangerous situations and intervene as soon as possible. Support programs for victims of gender-based violence and their children will be created and reinforced. Gender-based cyberviolence⁴ is also included in this policy.

6.6 Policy on harassment and discrimination prohibited by law

In Spain the Ley Orgánica 3/2007, de 22 de marzo, para la Igualdad Efectiva de Mujeres y Hombres, BOE núm. 71, de 23 de marzo de 2007, (Organic Law 3/2007, of 22 of March, for the Effective Equality Between Women and Men), aims to:

1. Making effective the right to equal treatment and opportunities between women and men, particularly by eradicating discrimination against women, no matter what their circumstances or conditions are, in whatever area of life it is discussed, and specifically in the political, civil,

⁴ Gender-based cyberviolence is a term designated to refer to gender-based violence but using technological devices. Cyber harassment or sextorsion are some examples of this type of violence against women.

labour, economic, social and cultural spheres to, following articles 9,2 and 14 of the Spanish Constitution, to achieve a more democratic, fairer and more supportive society.

2. It establishes the principles of actions of the Public Authorities, regulates the rights and duties of natural or legal persons, including public or private, and foresees measures destined to eliminate and correct in the public and private sectors all forms of discrimination related to gender.

Regarding sexual harassment and harassment related to gender, the same law has a specific article about it: Article 62 is called *Protocolo de actuación frente al acoso sexual y al acoso por razón de sexo* (Protocol of action against sexual harassment and gender-related harassment).

To prevent sexual harassment and gender related harassment, the General State Administration will negotiate with the legal representatives of the workers of said institution, the protocol of action which will, at least, cover the following principles:

- a) The agreement of the General Estate Administration and of the public institutions linked to or dependant of it, of preventing and not tolerating sexual harassment and gender-related harassment.
- b) The establishment of training for all members of the staff in order for them to know that they are obliged to respect the dignity of all people and their right to privacy, as well as equal treatment of women and men.
- c) To preserve the confidentiality of the reports of situations that could be considered sexual harassment or gender-related harassment without prejudice to what is established in the disciplinary regime regulations.
- d) Identify the people responsible for assisting those who make a complaint or denunciation.

6.7 Protocol against sexual and gender-related harassment

The UCM has agreed to be part of the National Treaty of Estate Against Gender-Based Violence. As sexual and gender-related harassment conducts can be complex and diverse, this protocol aims to treat each case individually and integrally, to ensure the people involved feel safe and accompanied, with total respect towards the personal circumstances and in a framework where the social and democratic estate of the law is always the reference.

The aim of the protocol and its objectives:

The aim of the UCM Protocol against Sexual and Gender-Related Harassment is to create a university free of harassment as a safe space, activating the processes and specific resources, when necessary, always following the guiding principles of comprehensive, permanent, and urgent care from professional specialists.

The Unidad de Igualdad (Gender Equality Unit), which is a dependent unit of the Delegación del Rector para Igualdad (Rector's Delegation for Equality), is the entity entitled to act when

cases of sexual or gender harassment occur. They support the victims who ask for advice or present a report to the Unit to ensure the necessary support as well as to prevent any risk of vulnerability.

Regarding objectives, this protocol has one general objective and several specific objectives:

- Main objective: Create a community in the university where sexual or sex-related harassment is prevented while acting with guarantees when the harassment happens.
- Specific objectives:
 - o Establishing a protocol of action with guarantees against sexual or gender-related harassment.
 - o Guaranteeing psychological and social support for the victim or victims, independently if they decide to fill in a report. In the case of students, guaranteeing the accompaniment, the attention, and the pedagogical guidance.
 - o Creating a protection and assistance program for victims and adopting the necessary measures to refer them to the appropriate resources, independently if they decide to fill in a police report.
 - o Guaranteeing the safety and dignity of all the people involved at all times.
 - o Preventing sexual and/or gender-related harassment in the university environment.

Scope of application: Who is protected by it.

As the objective scope of application, this protocol establishes a procedure of action to intervene and prevent possible sexual or gender related harassment conducted in the UCM. In order to produce a suspension or for the Unidad de Igualdad (Gender Equality Unit) to intervene, said conduct must happen inside any space of the campus, its schools, departments, or university facilities or outside them, if and when the conduct/misconduct happens in the setting of an activity organised by the UCM or is linked to a professional or educative relationship. This protocol also protects members who are linked to the UCM through any type of relationship and also includes individuals who are acting as legal guardians of UCM students or are colleagues of UCM students in companies, organisations, or in the UCM itself.

What can Unidad de Igualdad do?

- The first thing that needs to be done is filling out a report at the Gender Equality Unit. To do it a meeting in the Unidad de Igualdad (Gender Equality Unit) must be requested. It can be through phone or email.
- The victim can go to the meeting accompanied if they wish. They will explain their situation or the events to the specialised staff from the Unit. The victim will also decide if they want to submit a police report or not. Independent of this decision the victim will be informed of all the resources available in the psychological or social area.

- The process will only start when the report in the Unit is signed. The victim will be accompanied and advised by specialised staff from the Gender Equality Unit.
- The victim must be identified. The person who allegedly generated this harassment must be also identified. The report must be presented by the person affected. Anonymous reports or reports without the physical or digital signature of the victim will not be admitted.

Presenting a report at the Unidad de Igualdad (Gender Equality Unit) is not always necessary. There are other options:

- A request or advising meeting can be arranged. It can be done by the person who is suffering the harassment or people from their environment, academic authorities etc. This assistance can be in person, by the phone, or by email.
- If the person who is suffering this harassment does not want to present a report, they can warn the unit about the sexual or gender related harassment that is happening. This way the unit can activate the measure they consider appropriate.

Process of intervention:

Whenever the Equality Unit intervenes, the intervention model is based on the principle of due diligence for the investigation of Human Rights Violations.

Whenever there is a case of sexual and/or gender-related harassment and the victim decides to fill in a report in the Unidad de Igualdad (Gender Equality Unit) there are two possibilities:

- In the event that an extremely serious case is detected, this will be brought to the attention of the prosecutor's office, or the police, and the university will act ex officio.
- In the rest of the cases, reports will be sent to the Comisión Técnica y de Garantías (Technical and Guarantees Commission) for assessment and/ or evaluation. Depending on whether/on the case involves students or workers the representatives of the students or workers must be present at the commission too. They will have to meet in the following 48h working hours and evaluate the case, deciding if they need an external report by one or two experts.

The Comisión Técnica y de Garantías final report will be sent to la Delegada o Delegado del Rector para Igualdad (Gender Equality Rector's Delegate), and it will include recommendations for:

- Sending the case to Inspección de Servicios (Service inspection)
- Referring to psychological or psychosocial support for any of the involved individuals.
- Preventive intervention measures for any of the involved parties (for example, relocating the victim and their children (if relevant). Other measures may include helping the victim find a job, adapting their classes if the person who harassed them is a student).
- Mediation measures will be explored/implemented, explicitly for cases where gender-based violence has not happened.

- Closing the file if no acts constituting a crime have occurred.
- In the case the report is not admitted by the Comisión Técnica y de Garantías (Technical and Guarantees Commission) an appeal may be filed with the rector within a month.

La Comisión Técnica y de Garantías (Technical and Guarantees Commission) will be able to request to Delegada o Delegado del Rector para Igualdad (the Rector's Delegate for Gender Equality) the urgent need of applying preventive measures when:

- o A very serious administration crime or infraction is detected.
- o An urgent need for psychological, pedagogical, and or social intervention is detected for any of the parties/individuals involved in the case.
- o Risks are detected for any of the parties that may affect their physical, moral, psychological, academic, or social integrity.

Urgent or preventative measures proposed will always aim to prevent any risks for those who present the reports or for other people who are involved in the events or the procedures.

The Technical and Guarantees Commission) considers it necessary to interview the victim, the latter could ask for psychological or pedagogical accompaniment from the Dispositivo de Atención Psicológica (Psychological Attention Device).

The Technical and Guarantees Commission will try to prevent interviewing the alleged perpetrator when there is evidence of administrative suspension, and it will be referred to Inspección de Servicios (inspection service of the institution) to avoid duplicating the procedure.

Lastly, the Technical and Guarantees Commission will be able to collect testimonies from the people involved in the events, as well as run all the tests necessary to clarify them, respecting the current terms and the procedural guarantees established in the current legislation, as well as respecting the rights of all the people involved.

6.8 Tailored mentoring

Tailored mentoring, currently under development, is focused on creating a support network formed by women to empower women in the institution. This tailored mentoring is not limited to student-professor relationships but extends to the entire cohort of women inside and outside of the UCM.

7. Best practices from URCA

7.1 Gender and sexual violence

From 8 April to 7 June 2022, all students and staff at the University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne (URCA) were invited to take part in a major anonymous survey on living conditions and exposure to gender-based and sexual violence (GBV) during the 2021-2022 academic year. The acts that can be qualified as GBV identified in the survey include mockery (including 'humorous' remarks), contemptuous attitudes, demeaning remarks, acts of discrimination, questions about private life, obscene remarks, mimicking of sexual gestures, dissemination of pornographic images, insistent sexual propositions (including "in a humorous way"), non-consensual touching of the body, whether non-sexual (shoulders, arms, hair, face) or sexual (breasts, buttocks, thighs, sex), and attempted and non-consensual sexual intercourse.

The survey was distributed to all university's stakeholders, and it received more than 3,000 responses. It provided students and staff with the opportunity to anonymously report instances of violence that they had experienced and seek support if desired.

797 staff members responded to this survey, i.e., 32.2%, representative of all staff members in terms of campus or age, with a greater participation of women (62.5%). This strong community involvement emphasized that women are primarily affected as victims of gender-based and sexual violence (GBV).

Out of all the responses, there were 162 incidents that could be categorized as instances of sexist and sexual violence. These incidents ranged from 75 cases of mocking or contemptuous attitudes to 2 instances of non-consensual sexual acts. Unfortunately, these highly concerning incidents were not reported, which prevented the university from taking appropriate action. Additionally, it is worth noting that there are numerous instances of sexist comments within the university community, which is unacceptable.

More equal student participation

A total of 2,277 students responded to the survey, i.e., 8.6% of the URCA student population, and the sample was again considered to be representative. Not surprisingly, women are the primary victims of sexist and sexual violence. However, female students were only slightly over-represented among the respondents. This higher participation of students may indicate that they have a greater awareness of issues related to sexual and gender-based violence (GBV) compared to older individuals.

Out of the total number of responses, 498 incidents were identified as cases of sexual and gender-based violence, ranging from 191 instances of taunting or contemptuous attitudes to 3 cases of non-consensual sex. Once again, these extremely serious incidents were not reported, which hindered the university's ability to intervene. The survey also revealed that the majority of GBV incidents occur within the student community.

Overall, the study revealed that any form of violence has a negative impact on the career paths of staff members and the academic progress of students. While the number of reported

serious incidents was relatively low, the study demonstrates that even seemingly minor acts can have significant and long-lasting consequences for the victims. It is important to note that victims affected by sexist and sexual violence often confide in their colleagues, friends, or family members, but do not initiate formal proceedings within URCA.

Despite the establishment of a listening and support unit for victims of gender-based and sexual violence at URCA since 2018, which allows for a reporting process to be implemented, the study revealed that not all victims reported their experiences. In fact, during the same period, only six reports were submitted to the institution's legal affairs department, none of which involved the most severe cases identified in the survey. It is crucial to emphasize that without a formal report, the university cannot take individual action to support the victims.

This initial assessment of sexist and sexual violence at URCA has helped identify the challenges and risks faced during the academic year. The objective of this process is to develop an appropriate action plan to support students and staff, as well as to raise awareness about sexual and gender-based violence within the entire university community. Consequently, the reporting system has been modified to enhance its visibility.

A new survey will be conducted in the spring of 2023.

7.2 Policy on harassment and discrimination prohibited by law

The different faculties of the University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne (URCA) apply the laws of the French Republic relating to the principle of equality, excluding all discrimination and all violence.

1. Gender equality

After a long inventory, the URCA has recently drafted a gender equality action plan (<https://www.univ-reims.fr/media-files/38846/plan-d-action-egalite-des-genres.pdf> in French) with 4 main purposes:

- Evaluate, prevent, and address the gender pay gap.
- Guarantee equal access for women and men to bodies, grades, and jobs.
- Promoting the reconciliation of work and family life.
- Fight against sexual and gender-based violence, harassment, and discrimination.

URCA has made a commitment to accompany staff and students in the prevention and fight against sexual violence, harassment, and sexist behaviours. To support this effort, a specific mission called "Equality and Diversity" was established in 2019, led by Anaïs DANET. Its primary goal is to implement robust action plans in the areas of training and awareness regarding inequalities, discrimination, and violence related to sex, gender, and sexuality.

Additionally, the mission focuses on prevention and support for individuals who experience such forms of discrimination.

To enhance the fight against sexual violence, harassment, and sexist behaviours, URCA has developed a website that contains internal documents inspired by the guidelines provided by the Ministry of Higher Education, Research, and Innovation. The website can be found at <https://www.univ-reims.fr/vss/le-dispositif/le-dispositif,26213,43065.html>. Recognizing that it may not always be easy for victims to label the acts they have experienced, the site employs the gradation of acts outlined in the French penal code. It provides clear definitions and explanations of terms used in these situations to avoid any confusion about the nature of the offense and its categorization. Some of the defined terms include sexual harassment, sexual assault, hazing, sexual exhibitionism, cyberstalking, non-public insult, sexist abuse, rape, and voyeurism.

In summary, URCA is intensifying its actions on this particular topic by:

- Offering a training program to the entire community.
- Strengthening reporting mechanisms and their functioning.
- Organizing prevention and support for individuals with the Sexist and Sexual Violence service.
- Providing a permanent and continuous information system and strengthening communication.
- Acting for oneself and for others - within the institution: knowing the tools available to fight against these forms of moral and physical violence and the mechanisms for reporting situations at the institutional level.

2. Discrimination

As part of its anti-discrimination plan, in addition to the actions taken on equality and diversity with a particular emphasis on gender, the URCA has set up three different missions, each of which is responsible for one aspect of the anti-discrimination plan.

Disability

The French legislation proposes a definition of disability: Article 2-I, 1° of the law of February 11, 2005, for equal rights and opportunities, participation and citizenship of disabled persons, taken from Article 114 of the Code of Social Action and Families, which states: Constitutes a disability, within the meaning of the present law, any limitation of activity or restriction of participation in life in society suffered in his or her environment by a person due to a substantial, lasting or definitive alteration of one or more physical, sensory, mental, cognitive or psychic functions, a multiple disabilities or a disabling health disorder.

To comply with this law, URCA has included in its plan to fight against discrimination, the "Disability" mission, whose pilot and referent is Olivier DEBARGE. With this mission, the URCA wants to offer, in a concrete way, the possibility for students with disabilities to access the

university, to follow training, to obtain a university diploma, to benefit from real autonomy, and to succeed in their professional integration. As an employer, URCA wishes to offer a social role through work to people with disabilities by maintaining the employment of the staff concerned and by developing its recruitment policy in favour of people who benefit from the employment obligation. In addition, the establishment wants to be able to develop the accessibility of adequate and diversified services.

The University has also signed the Romain Jacob "Training" Charter (see <https://www.univ-reims.fr/media-files/18621/charte-romain-jacob.pdf> in French), which expresses its commitment to act in favour of people with disabilities in the education and training of health professionals.

Laicity and the fight against racism and anti-Semitism

The French law of July 8, 2013, known as the "Refoundation of the School of the Republic", reaffirms the fight against all forms of discrimination and violence and works to respect the equal dignity of all human beings, freedom of conscience, and laicity. The Inter-ministerial Delegation for the Fight against Racism, Anti-Semitism, and Anti-LGBT Hatred (DILCRAH) monitors the national plan's actions and supports associations, the academic world, and communities. In 2023, a new national plan against hate and discrimination is presented by the French government (see <https://www.gouvernement.fr/actualite/un-nouveau-plan-national-contre-la-haine-et-les-discriminations> in French). The objective for the period 2023-2026 is summarized in five points: Measure the reality of racism, anti-Semitism, and discrimination; Dare to name the reality of hatred; Better education and training; Sanction the perpetrators; Accompany the victims.

To reach these objectives, a Racism and Anti-Semitism referent, Olivier DUPERON, has been appointed. His mission is mainly to:

- Support and promote the implementation of national plans.
- Be the interlocutor and representative of the URCA for the different delegations, such as those for LGBT phobia (DILCRAH) and against Racism and Anti-Semitism (CORA), as well as within the network of "Racism, Anti-Semitism, Diversity, Equality, Discrimination and Secularism" referents of the universities.
- Implement preventive measures and reporting protocols.
- Act as an interlocutor and mediator for any person (agent, student) faced with such a situation.
- Disseminate a culture of law and a better knowledge of the principle of secularism through conferences or animations on campus, in collaboration with the URCA Law Faculty and the network of associations, as well as through the distribution of the CPU's legal guide on laicity.

Ethic et Deontology

The ethics section of the law of April 20, 2016, updates the general status of public agents and reaffirms the obligations of dignity, impartiality, integrity, probity, neutrality, and respect for

laicity. As a result, the function of deontologist was created and the deontologist referent is responsible, by law, for addressing requests for advice from agents and providing them with guidance. The professional deontologist's activity is covered by professional secrecy to protect the agent and to guarantee the independence of the deontologist in the exercise of his mission. The penalties for agents who have committed a breach of the duty of probity are significant, ranging from 5 years' imprisonment and a fine of €5,000 to 10 years' imprisonment and a fine of €1,000,000, depending on the level of the offence.

The circular letter of March 15, 2017 defines scientific integrity and introduces the policy for its respect within higher education and research institutions.

In compliance with it, URCA has signed the ethical charter (see <https://www.univ-reims.fr/media-files/22573/charte-ethique-version-definitive-apres-commission-12-septembre.pdf> in French). In addition, since 2018, an advisory body has been tasked with advising on ethical and deontological issues specific to the URCA. This commission in 2023 is composed among others with the president Mr. Guillaume GELLÉ, the vice-president in charge of Ethics and Deontology Mrs. Anne JUSSIAUME and a qualified external personality. This committee is particularly active in the areas of:

- Scientific integrity (honesty, respect for intellectual property, ...), prevention and fight against scientific fraud.
- Ethical supervision of research (respecting human and animal dignity and the environment).
- Fight against discrimination.
- Rights and obligations of public agents (support for the deontologist referent).
- Ethical supervision of video protection.

8. Best practices from SSST

8.1 Variety and diversity of staff and students in representative bodies, chairholders, and recipients of awards

The first SSST GEP was implemented in September 2022. SSST has a strong female presence within representative bodies and chairholders. Thus, this is not a result of applying measures to attain such a situation. Gender-segregated data is still not available for the SSST award recipients.

Possible contributing factors regarding positive trends are:

- SSST is a young institution that does not have deeply rooted traditional roles.
- SSST employs academics that have been educated abroad and have limited possibilities of attaining academic positions at more traditional, state-run Universities. At state Universities,

a traditional academic path is obtaining the first, second, and third cycle of higher education at that institution before being employed in academic roles.

- SSST academics, have rich international experience, and strive for diversity and equality.

However, SSST does not expect that these numbers will necessarily remain positive, so the plan is to monitor these data and design and apply the measures accordingly.

Also, SSST will gather gender-segregated data for award recipients and design measures in the next GAP version if such data turns out to be non-balanced.

9. Some concluding remarks

The plan to initiate a process of harmonisation of the GEPs of the partner institutions of the EDIRE project was carried out in three phases:

A comprehensive understanding of each GEP was obtained through online seminars, followed by a review of the documentation provided by each partner institution.

Detailed analysis of the initiatives focused not only on gender equality, but also on EDI offered by each partner college (Annex A).

The exchange of information on the initiatives deemed most interesting by each partner based on their own needs (**Annex B**). This exchange will occur in two phases: the exchange of written information, as described in this document, and the organisation of a series of online bilateral or multilateral webinars, which will be documented in the EDIRE project deliverables on the website.

Thus, this is a work in progress that allows SSST to adopt proven strategies from other universities while encouraging the other partner institutions to reflect on their own models and strategies.

SSST is committed to implementing GEP activities at the University, started in September 2022, with a specific focus on promoting work-life balance, supporting career progression, enhancing institutional governance, and fostering inclusive knowledge practices. These initiatives are aligned with both EDIRE's efforts and the principles of equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI). In the upcoming period, SSST will conduct the first revision of the GEP, involving the planning of new activities and updates to existing ones, spanning a duration of four years. The primary emphasis will be on organising workshops and training sessions that are carefully scheduled to align with both the GEP and EDIRE timelines, incorporating essential elements such as research. Furthermore, SSST's activities will strive to advance professional development and enhance the academic profiles of all individuals, in accordance with the new university-level regulations.

As a University, SSST is fully dedicated to creating the most inclusive environment for its diverse staff and student community. In pursuit of this goal, SSST continually develops and implements new rules and procedures that prioritise the protection of their rights and foster

a safe, supportive, and inclusive atmosphere, guided by the principles of equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI). It is important to acknowledge that the successful implementation of these activities may encounter challenges, including limited resources and staffing capacity, which could impact the extent of dedication to all procedures.

For TU Dublin their main strength is the move towards a holistic EDI approach while keeping a gender focus. Progress made on intersectional approaches to data collection, policy design and implementation. Apart from covering main inequality grounds, EDI policy covers main areas of intervention and university communities. A weakness is the very delayed EDI policy for research and the community of researchers. Also, some inequality grounds such as social class and age are not yet covered in policy.

The URCA has developed a gender equality action plan, aiming to address gender pay gaps, ensure equal access to opportunities, promote work-life balance, and combat sexual and gender-based violence. The university has missions dedicated to disability support, fighting racism and anti-Semitism, respecting laicity, and promoting ethics and deontology. URCA has implemented measures such as training programs, reporting mechanisms, and awareness campaigns to combat discrimination and support individuals affected by various forms of violence. Overall, URCA is actively working to create a safe and inclusive environment for its students and staff by intensifying efforts in prevention, support, reporting, and communication. Also, as for Dublin, some inequality grounds such as social class and age are not yet covered in the policy.

UniGE coordinated the Task work and, like the other partners, initiated an internal reflection on its EDI-related activities. Moreover, the comparison and the more profound understanding of the partner countries' approaches helped clarify some issues discussed in Italy since the GEPs became mandatory for Horizon Europe applications. The primary internal consideration relates to the large number of initiatives and offices that have been working on EDI for years. In many cases, these initiatives are governed by Italian law. On the one hand, this apparent dispersion strengthens the existing initiatives, as they are deeply rooted in the academic context. However, it also risks making the GEPs less meaningful as, without knowing the Italian general context, they may give the impression that many initiatives and strategies still need to be implemented. Therefore, the next GEP will need to outline better the complexity of existing initiatives that are not included in the GEP, possibly using charts and tables.

The issues discussed in Italy concern the construction of GEPs by Italian universities, which has followed different paths. It often started with Positive Action Plans (PAPs) and Gender Budgets (GB), which already included disaggregated gender data and a list of actions to promote gender equality approved by the academic senate. However, this transfer of actions from two existing documents, one of which, the PAP, has been mandatory for all Italian public institutions since 2011, raised some concerns. GEPs will remain mandatory throughout Horizon Europe, and this requirement is hoped to be confirmed and expanded in the following framework program. However, GEPs are currently less binding for universities than PAPs, which are governed by national legislation. Therefore, a debate is emerging on how to ensure the significance of PAPs without removing their gender-related functions or reducing their number.

The UCM II Gender Equality Plan works towards making sure there is no pay gap between men and women but aims to extend this sense of equality into governance boards, hiring, research teams and projects. When it comes to teaching, UCM wants to make sure the gender perspective is also included in lectures and seminars and, in order to evaluate it, has added those parameters to the teaching and self-assessment tool: DOCENTIA-UCM. However, it is important to notify that during the development of the current deliverable, some courses such as Language and Cultural courses have an unbalanced inclusion of the gender perspective in their classes so far. It is important to mention that, alongside the measures mentioned, the UCM has established a very solid protocol against sexual and gender-based harassment that protects all members of the university, no matter what role they have in the institution. This protocol is coordinated by the Unidad de Igualdad (Gender Equality Unit) and it has a very clear action plan for each case, in which psychological and social support is offered throughout the process.

Through the process of sharing the different GEP's, it has been detected that the UCM has still room for improvement, especially when it comes to collecting data and statistics about its members but also its role in making visible the relevance of its female academics in the different fields. Lastly, UCM has to work on the inclusion of gender equality in organisational culture, as well as the inclusion of the EDI principles.

In conclusion, it is essential to emphasise that the information exchange among the partners is ongoing, and seminars are being planned to explore further the themes that have emerged from the collaborative work on GEPs. The impact on the future GEPs of the partners has yet to be visible. However, the interest in strategies adopted in other countries, as evidenced by this document, demonstrates concrete possibilities for implementing changes based on activities that other universities have successfully tested. This increases the likelihood of success and positive impact.

Every new activity will be made available on the EDIRE project website and will be promoted through its social media channels and networks.

Annex A

Annex A identifies the existing measures promoting gender equality and EDI in each partner university. For each measure, there are three options: Y - the measure is active and running; IP - the measure is planned and its implementation is a work in progress; N - the measure is not active and not planned. The annex has been divided into six sections to facilitate readability.

Annex A _ Identifying the existing measures promoting gender equality and EDI				
Section 1_Macro area Engendering Knowledge				
	Y	N	IP*	
Training (staff and students)	TUD		SSST	

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	URCA		UCM	
GE Awareness raising	TUD URCA	UCM	SSST	
Anti-bias training	UniGE TUD URCA		SSST UCM	
Gender in STEM	TUD URCA	UCM	SSST	
Change management processes	TUD UCM		SSST UNIGE	
Integration of gender knowledge into teaching in all disciplines	UCM		SSST	
GE in Language/cultural courses	TUD UCM URCA		SSST UniGE	
Gender and organisational change courses	TUD UCM URCA		SSST UniGE	
Build gender awareness into Research Design & Practice	TUD		SSST UniGE UCM	
Promote sex/gender analysis and EDI in science	UCM			
Inclusion of gender equality criteria using the UCM-DOCENTIA program for the evaluation and self-assessment for professors and students.				

Annex A _ Identifying the existing measures promoting gender equality and EDI				
Section 2_Macro area Career progression development and support				
Raising profile of Academics	Y	N	IP	
Gender aware Academic/Administrative leadership programmes	TUD UCM URCA		SSST	
Gender balanced External Lecturers and Visiting professors	TUD	SSST UCM UniGE URCA		
Tailored mentoring	TUD UCM	SSST UniGE		

	URCA			
Early career research support	TUD UCM	SSST UniGE		
Female scientific experts' database	UniGE	SSST URCA	UCM	
Take into account breaks and part time work in career evaluations	UniGE TUD URCA	SSST UCM		
Encourage gender balance in candidate pools	TUD	UCM URCA	SST UniGE	
Skills training: media, funding, management, etc.		SSST UCM UniGE	URCA	
Tailored support/personal coaching	TUD URCA	SSST UCM UniGE		
Promote gender perspective and gender balance of research teams.			UCM	

Annex A _ Identifying the existing measures promoting gender equality and EDI				
Section 3_Macro area Work-life balance				
Policy; Culture and management practices	Y	N	IP	
Childcare and dependent care provision	TUD URCA	SSST UniGE	UCM	
Sabbaticals for staff returning from extended caring leave	TUD URCA	SSST UCM UniGE		
Supports for careers, flexible working arrangements.	TUD URCA	SSST UniGE	UCM	
Question the requirement for geographical mobility		SSST UCM UniGE		
Boosting measures that guarantee a culture of co-responsibility			UCM	
Design and dissemination of an awareness campaign about work-personal life balance and co-responsibility.			UCM	
Publication of service catalogue about family conciliation and co-responsibility			UCM	

Encouragement of going back to work in a remote format to establish family conciliation and co-responsibility between administrative staff.			UCM	
Enforce compliance of digital curfew right for university professors, staff and students.			UCM	

Annex A _ Identifying the existing measures promoting gender equality and EDI				
Section 4_ Macro area Structural measures: institutional governance, engagement of decision makers				
National schemes to promote equality, diversity and inclusion (or one of them)	Y	N	IP	
Gender pay audit	TUD UCM URCA	SSST		
Gender budget	UniGE		UCM	
Key performance indicators and targets	TUD URCA	SSST	UniGE UCM	
Pledges from University Governance supporting GE and EDI	TUD UCM URCA	UniGE	SSST	
Promotion of diversity in decision-making bodies	SST TUD URCA	UniGE	UCM	
Code of conduct/non-discrimination policy	UniGE TUD URCA	SSST	UCM	
Positive actions	UniGE TUD URCA	SSST	UCM	
Positive discrimination		SSST	UCM	
Quotas (Gender and underrepresented groups)		SSST	UCM	
Set gender equality as an institutional priority	TUD UCM URCA	UniGE	SSST	
Gender balance in scientific leadership and decision-making positions		UniGE	SSST	

			UCM	
Join the mainstream flux (EU and other supranational organisations),	UCM			
Measures to eliminate gender pay gaps			UCM	
Creating an inventory of the database in the institution communication system that includes the gender variable.	UNIGE		UCM	
Gender equality criteria in subcontracting processes.			UCM	
EDI monitoring and support units			UCM	
Establishing internal EDI networks			UCM	
Channels to address gender equality/EDI concerns and complaints				
Policy on Harassment & Discrimination Prohibited by Law	UniGE TUD UCM CA			
Policy against Sexual Violence	UniGE TUD UCM URCA			
Senior Equity & Inclusion Advisor	TUD	UCM		
Ombudsman		UCM		
Data collection, data analyses disaggregated by gender and other criteria (disability, age, etc.	TUD UCM URCA		UniGE	
Gendered language and terminology, revision of existing documents/texts/templates	UCM URCA		UniGE	
Other (you may add as many lines as you need)				

Annex A _ Identifying the existing measures promoting gender equality and EDI				
Section 5_A Prevention and action against sexual harassment and/or sexism	Y	N	IP	
Anonymous reporting tools	TUD URCA			
Activation of the protocol against sexual harassment and/ or sexism of the II GEP of the UCM	UCM			
Support for survivors			UCM	
Designing and developing an Integral Formation Plan about sexual or sexist harassment			UCM	
Awareness raising about sexual harassment and sexist behaviour			UCM	
Section 5_B Preventing and acting against gender violence in the National Pact against Gender Based Violence Framework	Y	N	IP	
Offering psychological and social assistance to the victims of gender-based violence	UCM			
Signing agreements with special resources specialised in gender-based violence			UCM	
Publication of guide against sexual assault	UCM			
Financial support and housing measures for victims of gender-based violence, including their sons			UCM	
Financial support and housing measures for refugees			UCM	
Creation of a university network to fight against gender-based violence			UCM	

Annex A _ Identifying the existing measures promoting gender equality and EDI				
Section 6_ Building up an equality culture (Section present in the UCM GEP	Y	N	IP	
Inclusive language in the institution			UCM	
Creating and disseminating guides about inclusive language	UCM			
Including the gender perspective in diverse activities within the academic community				
Inclusion of gender specific modules, courses and seminars in the studies plan			UCM	
Inclusion of the gender perspective in sport and cultural activities			UCM	
Programs of coexisting values with a gender perspective inside the university community			UCM	
Inclusion of the gender perspective in the workplace hazard prevention plan				
Including gender perspective in the workplace hazard prevention plan			UCM	
Design and dissemination of programs that promote women's health			UCM	
Awareness of specific procedures regarding risk pregnancy, postpartum and breastfeeding phase			UCM	
Raising awareness of woman researchers, feminism and gender research and actions that encourage gender equality				
Promoting and supporting research projects about feminism and gender	UCM			
Funding programs for projects in gender studies led by women researchers			UCM	
Awards for thesis and masters' and degree final projects in gender and feminism			UCM	
Dissemination of the work developed by women in STEM	UCM			
Dissemination of the work regarding feminism and gender perspective done by female researchers in the institution	UCM		UniG	
Creation of a directory of women experts of different knowledge areas			UCM	
Establishing the Gender Equality mark in the institution				
Communication and dissemination with gender perspective			UCM	
Design and development of an Integral Plan in Formation about Gender for all members of the university			UCM	
Promoting the leadership of the Equality Unit in other university networks			UCM	
Encouraging gender research groups and international academic networks in gender perspective			UCM	

Collaborative networks between feminist and gender perspective NGOs and female researchers in the university			UCM	
Promote research groups and international academic networks in gender perspective	UCM			
Dissemination of the gender equality actions through the social media			UCM	
Fomenting the creation and establishment of NGOs with gender perspective (specially by students).			UCM	

Annex B

After becoming familiar with the GEPs and other EDI-related activities organized by the Partners, each organization selected the topics addressed by others that they wanted to learn more about. This information was recorded in Annex B. To enhance the readability of the annex, let us illustrate the first row: concerning the topic of "Gender awareness raising," it is evident from Annex A and the analysis of the Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) that both TUD and URCA present compelling content. URCA and SSST have expressed keen interest in further exploring the insights provided by TUD, while UCM has indicated an interest in the content offered by URCA. In the coming months, information exchanges will be arranged for all the topics listed in the Annex.

Annex B. Exchange of knowledge and good practices

TOPIC	TUD	URCA	UCM	SSST	UniGE
<i>GE Awareness raising</i>	URCA, SSST	UCM	//	//	//
Anti-bias training	SSST	UniGE, UCM	//	//	//
Gender in STEM	UCM, URCA, UniGE	UniGE, SSST	//	//	
Change management processes	UniGE		//	//	//
Integration of gender knowledge into teaching in all disciplines	URCA	//		//	//
GE in Language/cultural courses	//	//	UniGE	//	//
Build gender awareness into Research Design & Practice	UniGE, SSST	UniGE, SSST	UniGE, SSST	//	//
Promote sex/gender analysis and EDI in science	UCM, URCA	//	//	//	//
UCM-DOCENTIA program to evaluate the inclusion of gender perspective in teaching activities.	//	//	UniGE	//	//
	//	//	UniGE	//	//
Gender balanced External Lecturers and Visiting professors	UCM	//	//	//	//

Tailored mentoring	UniGE, SSST	UniGE, SSST	UniGE, SSST	//	//
Female scientific experts' database	UniGE, URCA	//	//	//	UCM, URCA
Tailored support/personal coaching	UniGE		//	//	//
Gender pay audit	SSST	SSST	SSST	//	//
Gender balance report	//	//	//	//	SSST
Key performance indicators and targets	URCA	URCA	//	//	//
Variety and diversity of staff and students in representative bodies, chairholders and recipients of awards	UniGE	UniGE	//		//
Policy on Harassment & Discrimination Prohibited by Law	SSST	SSST	SSST	//	SSST
Policy against Sexual Violence	SSST	SSST	SSST	//	SSST
Senior Equity & Inclusion Advisor	UCM, UniGE	//	//	//	//
Activation of the protocol against sexual harassment and/ or sexism of the II GEP of the UCM	//	//	SSST	//	//

Legenda: // the Partner does not mention the topic.

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